

A Cross-sectional Study Assessing the Lung Ultrasound as a Complementary Imaging Tool for Chest X-ray in the Evaluation of Dyspnea

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Abstract:

Aim: The aim of the present study was to assess the role of lung ultrasound: a complementary imaging tool for chest x-ray in the evaluation of dyspnea.

Material & methods: A cross-sectional study, conducted over the duration of one year in the Department of Radiology, Lord Buddha koshi medical college and Hospital, Saharsa, Bihar, India. The study population comprised 50 patients of either sex, presenting with a complaint of dyspnea. All patients with a clinical history suggestive of acute coronary syndrome as a cause of dyspnea, patients on invasive ventilatory support, or with suspected/known metabolic causes of dyspnea were excluded from the study.

Results: The most common non-translobar consolidation was seen “Fractal sign/shred sign.” Translobar consolidation was identified by the “Lung sign.” Six patients with “Unilateral lung rockets” were also diagnosed with pneumonia. Pleural effusion was found in patients with pneumonia, pulmonary edema and hydropneumothorax in the study. Visualization of the “Lung line” identified was seen as the presence of pleural effusion. Internal septations and internal echoes were used to help characterize the collection as an empyema. Out of 50 cases included in our study, 46 cases showed concordant diagnosis on ultrasound and chest X-ray (92%). Chest X-ray was found to have a sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, and negative predictive value of 100%.

Conclusion: A high concordance was noted between ultrasound and chest X-ray for diagnosis of all pathologies studied ($p < 0.01$), the highest noted in pneumonia/pleural effusion and diffuse interstitial syndrome ($\kappa \frac{1}{4} 0.9$). Hence, ultrasound may be considered a complimentary imaging modality for Chest-X-ray in the evaluation of dyspnoea.

Keywords: A-Lines, B-Lines, Dyspnoea, Lung Ultrasound, Pneumonia, Emergency

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Introduction

For many years ultrasound has not been employed for the evaluation of the lung.[1] All diagnostic ultrasound methods are based on the principle that ultrasound is reflected by an interface between media with different acoustic impedance. In

normal conditions, with aerated lungs, the ultrasound beam finds the lung air and no image is visible, because no acoustic mismatch may reflect the beam, which is rapidly dissipated by air.[2] Lung ultrasound demonstrated in the last decade

to be of significant value in the clinical assessment of different pleuro-pulmonary disorders.[3,4] It is a complementary diagnostic tool, and a valuable guide for both diagnostic and therapeutic interventional procedures.[3,5] In the last decade, many studies focused on the role of LUS in the early differential diagnosis of patients with acute dyspnea from different causes.[6-8] In particular, LUS demonstrated to have a valuable accuracy, in combination with clinical findings, in the diagnosis of pneumonia.[9,10]

One of the most important and recognized application of

LUS in clinical practice is for the detection and characterization of pleural effusions and as a guide for thoracentesis.[11] The routine use of LUS in the assessment of pleural effusion before and during the execution of the thoracentesis demonstrated to significantly reduce the rate of thoracentesis related complications.[11,12] Historical data reported a 0.5% occurrence of pneumothorax in case of LUS-guided thoracentesis, compared to a prevalence ranging from 7 to 15% when LUS is not used.[13] Lung ultrasound demonstrated in the last decade to be of significant value in the clinical assessment of different pleuro-pulmonary disorders.[14] It is a complementary diagnostic tool, and a valuable guide for both diagnostic and therapeutic interventional procedures demonstrated to have a valuable accuracy, in combination with clinical findings, in the diagnosis of pneumonia.[6,15-17] One of the most important and recognized application of LUS in clinical practice is for the detection and characterization of pleural effusions and as a guide for thoracentesis.[11] The routine use of LUS in the assessment of pleural effusion before and during the execution of the thoracentesis demonstrated to significantly reduce the rate of thoracentesis related complications.[11,12] Finally, LUS is a valuable technique as guidance of percutaneous transthoracic needle biopsy,

with a rate of complications <0.5% in the case series.[18]

In recent years, lung ultrasound has gained popularity, particularly in the emergency and critical care units where it is used as point-of-care-ultrasound and has become an indispensable tool to the intensivist. Hence the aim of the study was to assess the role of lung ultrasound: a complementary imaging tool for chest x-ray in the evaluation of dyspnea.

Material & Methods

A cross-sectional study, conducted over the duration of one year in the Department of Radiology, Lord Buddha koshi medical college and Hospital, Saharsa, Bihar, India. The study population comprised 50 patients of either sex, presenting with a complaint of dyspnea. All patients with a clinical history suggestive of acute coronary syndrome as a cause of dyspnea, patients on invasive ventilatory support, or with suspected/known metabolic causes of dyspnea were excluded from the study.

Methodology

Relevant history, clinical examination, and laboratory findings were recorded. All patients underwent chest-X-ray and chest ultrasound. Each modality was interpreted by two different investigators, blinded to each other. The ultrasound examinations were performed and interpreted by the first author, who had been trained by a senior resident with nearly 6 years of experience in ultrasound. The images were reviewed by a consultant with more than 15 years of experience in ultrasound.

Longitudinal scans of the anterior and lateral chest wall were performed with the patient in the supine or semi-recumbent position. This was followed by an examination of the posterior chest wall with patient in the sitting position, depending on the clinical status of the patient. The lung chest wall interface showing the pleural line and various artifacts were imaged in all

cases on gray scale ultrasound and the findings were analyzed for the following features.

- Rib shadows and underlying pleural line for the “Batwing” appearance, and A-lines.
- Lung sliding on B and M modes.
- B-Lines: location, laterality, pattern based on number of B-lines.
- Collections: lung line, quad sign, septations, internal echoes, shred sign, sub-B-lines.
- Consolidation: fractal sign, C-line, lung sign, sonographic air–bronchograms.

A diagnosis was made based on the ultrasound findings for the cause of dyspnea, and appropriate lung profile as devised by the BLUE Protocol was assigned. Chest ultrasound findings were correlated with chest X-ray findings, and concordance was checked. Due to ethical considerations, CT scans could not be used as a reference standard. Final diagnosis at the time of discharge was considered the

gold standard for patients with no previous CT scans. However, in patients who had undergone a CT scan, findings were recorded in cases of discordance.

Statistical Analysis

The obtained data were entered in the MS-Excel and analyzed using the SPSS version 25.0. Qualitative data were expressed in percentage and statistical difference between the proportions were tested by chi-square test or Fischer’s exact test. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, and negative predictive value of chest X-ray and chest ultrasound were calculated for different pathologies. The concordance between chest ultrasound and chest X-ray findings was analyzed using Cohen’s kappa value with ‘p’ value less than 0.05 considered statistically significant.

Results

Table 1: Chest ultrasound features in patients with consolidation (n=50)

Imaging findings	Diagnostic categories showing consolidation			
	Consolidation with pleural effusion (n=30)	Consolidation only (n=16)	Hydropneumothorax/ Pneumothorax (n=4)	Total
‘Fractal sign’	24	8	4	40
‘Lung sign’	6	2	2	10
C-line	2	6	0	8
Air bronchogram	30	10	4	44
Effusion	30	0	4	34
Unilateral lung rocket	8	4	0	12
Irregular/thickened pleural line	4	10	2	16

The most common non-translobar consolidation was seen “Fractal sign/shred sign.” Translobar consolidation was identified by the “Lung sign.” Six patients with “Unilateral lung rockets” were also diagnosed with pneumonia.

Table 2: Chest ultrasound features in patients with Pleural effusion (n=50)

Imaging finding	Diagnostic categories showing pleural effusion				Total
	Pleural effusion only (n=8)	Consolidation with associated pleural effusion (n=30)	Pulmonary edema (n=8)	Hydro-pneumothorax (n=4)	
Lung line	8	30	8	4	50
Sinusoidal sign	6	28	6	4	44
Quad sign	8	24	4	4	40
Septations	4	8	0	0	12
Internal echoes	4	16	0	0	20
Shred/Fractal sign	0	28	0	2	30
Sub B-Lines	8	20	2	0	30

Pleural effusion was found in patients with pneumonia, pulmonary edema and hydropneumothorax in the study. Visualization of the “Lung line” identified was seen as the presence of pleural effusion. Internal septations and internal echoes were used to help characterize the collection as an empyema.

Table 3: Concordance of USG pathology with chest X-ray findings and Concordance of individual diagnoses on USG with chest X-ray findings

	No.	%
Concordance present	46	92
Concordance absent	4	8
Pathology	Concordance	Discordance
Pneumonia/pleural effusion	25	1
Pneumothorax/ hydropneumothorax	7	1
Interstitial lung disease (ILD)	5	0
Pulmonary edema	2	1
Acute exacerbation of COPD/asthma	7	0
Pulmonary infarct	0	1

Out of 50 cases included in our study, 46 cases showed concordant diagnosis on ultrasound and chest X-ray (92%).

Table 4: Comparison of Ultrasound and Chest-X Ray in ability to correctly diagnose the studied pathology

Pathology	Correctly diagnosed on USG	Correctly diagnosed on CXR	p-Value
Pneumothorax	9	7	0.98
Pulmonary edema	7	6	0.88
Pleural effusion/pneumonia	25	25	—
ILD	3	4	—
Acute exacerbation of COPD/asthma	5	7	0.45
Pulmonary infarct	1	0	—
Old Koch's with URTI	0	1	—

Chest X-ray was found to have a sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, and negative predictive value of 100%.

Discussion

Dyspnea is one of the most common presenting symptoms encountered in hospital admissions, with chest X-ray being the first-line radiological investigation ordered for its assessment. However, this modality has its limitations in the form of exposure to ionizing radiation and decreased sensitivity for certain findings in supine position. Although CT scan is the gold standard and offers the definitive diagnosis in cases of clinical dilemma, high cost and unavailability in resource poor settings apart from exposure to ionizing radiation hinder its feasibility in all cases.

The most common non-translobar consolidation was seen as "Fractal sign/shred sign." Translobar consolidation was identified by the "Lung sign." Six patients with "Unilateral lung rockets" were also diagnosed with pneumonia. Out of 50 cases included in our study, 45 cases showed concordant diagnosis on ultrasound and chest X-ray (90%). Consolidations due to infective lung disease are mostly visualized as mixed, hypo- and hyperechoic, or hypoechoic, images by LUS, with regular margins, and associated with pleural effusion in about half of the cases. Hyperechoic spots, defined by some authors as "air bronchogram," may be detected within lung consolidation by LUS in a significant percentage of cases, as well.[19] In this context, it is important to underline that this hyperechoic images does not match to the chest HRCT finding of the air bronchogram, as properly defined. Hence, operators should not be misled by the visualization of these hyperechoic spots within the lesions by LUS, as their clinical significance is not comparable to what observed by chest HRCT. This misleading may indeed lead to errors and confusion in the differential diagnosis.[20] Our findings were consistent with Mathis et al[21] with the infarcted region appearing as a

subpleural, hypoechoic wedge-shaped area with no doppler signal. Previously performed upper limb venous doppler had also revealed thrombus in right brachial and axillary vein. Chest X-ray was found to have a sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, and negative predictive value of 100%. The difference could be attributed to the small sample size and the fact that dyspnea was considered as the mandatory inclusion criteria for patient selection in our study and febrile patients with no respiratory distress were excluded. Hence, there were no radiographically occult cases. Diffuse interstitial syndrome[22,23] is diagnosed on ultrasound by demonstrating multiple (three or more) B-lines[24] in more than one scanning zone on the anterolateral chest, bilaterally. Diffuse interstitial syndrome is seen in pulmonary edema and interstitial lung disease.[25,26]

Conclusion

Ultrasound serves as a valuable imaging modality for the assessment of dyspnea. Ultrasound possesses the ability to diagnose prevalent respiratory pathologies that result in dyspnea, such as pneumonia, pneumothorax, pulmonary edema, and acute exacerbation of COPD/severe asthma. This capability stems from its noninvasive characteristics, wide accessibility, and absence of ionising radiation. Furthermore, ultrasound has traditionally been employed in the detection of pleural effusion. Additionally, it demonstrates a strong correlation with Chest X-ray, which is currently the primary imaging method used to assess dyspnea and diagnose these conditions. Therefore, it can be regarded as a supplementary imaging technique for this purpose.

References

1. Harrison's principles of internal medicine. New York, McGraw-Hill; 17 2008.

2. Lichtenstein DA: General Ultrasound in the Critically Ill. Berlin, Springer Verlag; II 2007.
3. Taylor A, Anjum F, O'Rourke MC. Thoracic and lung ultrasound. InStatPearls [Internet] 2022 Jun 19. StatPearls Publishing.
4. Chiappetta M, Meacci E, Cesario A, Smargiassi A, Inchingolo R, Ciavarella LP, Lopatriello S, Contegiacomo A, Congedo MT, Margaritora S. Postoperative chest ultrasound findings and effectiveness after thoracic surgery: A pilot study. *Ultrasound in medicine & biology*. 2018 Sep 1;44(9):1960-7.
5. Müller NL, Franquet T, Lee KS, Silva CI, editors. *Imaging of pulmonary infections*. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins; 2007.
6. Sperandeo M, Del Colle A, Frongillo E, Rea G, Dimitri L, Cipriani C, Lacedonia D. Safety maximization of percutaneous transthoracic needle biopsy with ultrasound guide in subpleural lesions in the evaluation of pulmonary consolidation. *Respiratory Research*. 2019 Dec;20(1):1-3.
7. Bekgoz B, Kilicaslan I, Bildik F, Keles A, Demircan A, Hakoglu O, Coskun G, Demir HA. BLUE protocol ultrasonography in Emergency Department patients presenting with acute dyspnea. *The American journal of emergency medicine*. 2019 Nov 1;37(11):2020-7.
8. Gargani L. Ultrasound of the lungs: more than a room with a view. *Heart failure clinics*. 2019 Apr 1;15(2):297-303
9. Sperandeo M, Varriale A, Sperandeo G, Polverino E, Feragalli B, Piattelli ML, Maggi MM, Palmieri VO, Terracciano F, De Sio I, Vilella M. Assessment of ultrasound acoustic artifacts in patients with acute dyspnea: a multicenter study. *Acta Radiologica*. 2012 Oct;53(8):885-92
10. Kameda T, Mizuma Y, Taniguchi H, Fujita M, Taniguchi N. Point-of-care lung ultrasound for the assessment of pneumonia: a narrative review in the COVID-19 era. *Journal of Medical Ultrasonics*. 2021 Jan;48:31-43.
11. Miles MJ, Islam S. Point of care ultrasound in thoracic malignancy. *Annals of Translational Medicine*. 2019 Aug;7(15).
12. Sperandeo M, Filabozzi P, Varriale A, Carnevale V, Piattelli ML, Sperandeo G, Brunetti E, Decuzzi M. Role of thoracic ultrasound in the assessment of pleural and pulmonary diseases. *Journal of ultrasound*. 2008 Jun 1;11(2):39-46.
13. Roy A. An application of linear mixed effects model to assess the agreement between two methods with replicated observations. *Journal of biopharmaceutical statistics*. 2009 Jan 2;19(1):150-73.
14. Taylor A, Anjum F, O'Rourke MC. Thoracic and lung ultrasound. InStatPearls [Internet] 2022 Jun 19. StatPearls Publishing.
15. Taylor A, Anjum F, O'Rourke MC. *Thoracic and Lung Ultrasound*. BTI Stat Pearls Publishing LLC (2020).
16. Kameda T, Mizuma Y, Taniguchi H, Fujita M, Taniguchi N. Point-of-care lung ultrasound for the assessment of pneumonia: a narrative review in the COVID-19 era. *Journal of Medical Ultrasonics*. 2021 Jan;48:31-43.
17. D'Amato M, Rea G, Carnevale V, Grimaldi MA, Saponara AR, Rosenthal E, Maggi MM, Dimitri L, Sperandeo M. Assessment of thoracic ultrasound in complementary diagnosis and in follow up of community-acquired pneumonia (cap). *BMC Medical Imaging*. 2017 Dec;17(1):1-8.
18. Sperandeo M, Trovato FM, Dimitri L, Catalano D, Simeone A, Martines GF, Piscitelli AP, Trovato GM. Lung transthoracic ultrasound elastography imaging and guided biopsies of subpleural cancer: a preliminary report. *Acta radiologica*. 2015 Jul;56(7):798-805
19. Chiappetta M, Meacci E, Cesario A, Smargiassi A, Inchingolo R, Ciavarella LP, Lopatriello S, Contegiacomo A, Congedo MT, Margaritora S. Postoperative chest ultrasound findings

- and effectiveness after thoracic surgery: A pilot study. *Ultrasound in medicine & biology*. 2018 Sep 1;44(9):1960-7.
20. Tinti MG, Cipriani C, De Cosmo S, Sperandeo M. Pneumothorax and air bronchogram in transthoracic ultrasound: basic considerations. *Ultrasound in Medicine and Biology*. 2019 Jun 1;45(6):1500.
 21. Mathis G, Dirschmid K. Pulmonary infarction: sonographic appearance with pathologic correlation. *European journal of radiology*. 1993 Nov 1;17(3):170-4.
 22. Lichtenstein DA. BLUE-protocol and FALLS-protocol: two applications of lung ultrasound in the critically ill. *Chest* 2015;147(06): 1659–1670.
 23. Lichtenstein D. *Lung Ultrasound in the Critically Ill: The BLUE Protocol*. Switzerland: Springer Nature; 2016.
 24. Reissig A, Kroegel C. Transthoracic sonography of diffuse parenchymal lung disease: the role of comet tail artifacts. *J Ultrasound Med* 2003;22(02):173–180.
 25. Reissig A, Copetti R. Lung ultrasound in community-acquired pneumonia and in interstitial lung diseases. *Respiration* 2014; 87(03):179–189.
 26. Buda N, Piskunowicz M, Porzezińska M, Kosiak W, Zdrojewski Z. Lung ultrasonography in the evaluation of interstitial lung disease in systemic connective tissue diseases: criteria and severity of pulmonary fibrosis - analysis of 52 patients. *Ultraschall Med* 2016;37(04):379–385.